

A network diagram background consisting of various sized blue and grey circular nodes connected by thin blue lines, forming a complex web of connections.

Monitoring of Dissemination Activities and Communication Material

Version 1

D7.2

March 2024

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Executive Summary

This document reports on the execution of the dissemination and communication strategy for ENERGATE, as laid out in D7.1 – Dissemination and Communication strategy. The reporting period spans between the January 2023 and February 2024.

The report includes a description of the communication and dissemination activities already carried out, measuring their performance in light of the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) targets.

Overall, the communication and dissemination strategy of ENERGATE is being executed according to plan. However, several KPI targets were prematurely achieved, which justifies the setting of stretch goals for some activities. On the other hand, some KPI require strategic adjustments in order to be in line with the communication and dissemination goals of the project.

ENERGATE has successfully achieved or is in good progress on 17 out of 18 KPIs. For the one underachieved KPI, a strategic approach has been implemented.

Communication, dissemination, and standardisation efforts in this reporting period include:

- The participation in the #SmartEnergyCluster with 20 other EU projects.
- The organisation of the 1st Regional Training Workshop in Madrid.
- The regular updating of the ENERGATE website
- The participation in the REHVA Brussels Summit and in the BIGG Final Event in 2023.
- The ongoing improvement of the project's communication materials, through the creation of new brochures, banners, and infographics.
- The highly successful presence of ENERGATE on social media.

The adjustment of some indicators and the setting of stretch goals justify an updated list of targets KPI for the final months of the ENERGATE project.

1. Introduction

This report is based on the dissemination and communication strategy designed in the ENERGATE report “Dissemination and Communication Strategy”¹. It begins with a description of the activities carried out, as well as their results and challenges encountered.

The performance of the dissemination activities is then assessed in light of the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) already established. This analysis supports a revision of the overall dissemination and communication strategy, which includes the adjustment of some targets, the revision of measurement rules, and the establishment of stretch goals that maximise impact.

Our approach, particularly during the initial phase when the platform was yet to come online, centered on the creation and dissemination of materials that comprehensively elucidate the benefits and functionalities of the ENERGATE platform. This proactive dissemination strategy ensures that all potential users gain early insights into the platform's benefits and interface. Such an approach is crucial for cultivating familiarity and anticipation, setting the stage for a highly engaged user base upon its launch.

Moreover, our focus on activities such as the development of dedicated webpages, engagement through social media, and direct communication with stakeholders is steered by the objective to reach the broadest possible audience. The document concludes with an updated table of dissemination and communication KPIs, which will be considered for the final months of ENERGATE.

¹https://energate-project.eu/sites/default/files/results/ENERGATE_D7.1-Dissemination%20and%20Communication%20Strategy-v1.00.pdf

2. Execution of the dissemination and communication strategy

Overall, the dissemination and communication strategy laid out from the beginning of the project has been successfully and timely executed. All partners have engaged actively in communication and dissemination activities, either by producing contents or reviewing them before release.

A more detailed activity description follows.

2.1. Visual identity

Communication activities for ENERGATE began with the creation of a project identity, which includes a logo, a set of colours, and a font. This identity derived into a brand manual, which provides guidelines for the use of all the project visual elements. All elements are included in ANNEX I of this document.

All the identity elements of ENERGATE are available to the consortium in the project shared folder. Nevertheless, partners are regularly reminded and encouraged to refer to the brand guidelines, so to ensure visual coherence among all outputs of the project.

2.2. Digital outreach

2.2.1. ENERGATE website network

The ENERGATE website is live since April 2023 live, transitioning from its initial development phase to a comprehensive platform. It serves as a pivotal resource for promoting the ENERGATE action, enhancing awareness among target groups, and attracting potential contributions. The site offers open access to public project results and supports result exploitation beyond the project's conclusion. It features essential project information, updates on events, and facilitates access to project outcomes.

As of **February 29th, 2024**, the ENERGATE website counted a total of 3,616 unique visitors. Detailed descriptions of website contents and page performance can be found in Annex II. All metrics are retrieved from Google Analytics.

Building on the momentum of the ENERGATE project's main website, we now shift focus to introduce the dedicated webpages created by our 12 consortium partners. These pages are designed to complement the central ENERGATE platform, offering more detailed insights into each partner's unique contributions and perspectives on the project. Through these dedicated spaces, partners share their experiences, advancements, and the specific roles they play within ENERGATE, enriching the project's narrative and outreach. ENERGATEENERGATE

Annex III includes a description for each partner's dedicated webpage.

2.2.2. ENERGATE social media

Our social media strategy during this period focused on leveraging targeted content, strategic hashtags, and partner engagement to enhance visibility and drive interaction. All metrics and insights reported for our social media pages (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube) are up to date as of February 29th, 2024.

Our Twitter channel, [@ENERGATE_eu](https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu), serves as a dynamic platform for sharing the latest updates, insights, and achievements of the ENERGATE project. It's designed to engage with our community, disseminate valuable information on energy efficiency, and foster discussions around sustainable building practices. Through regular tweets, we aim to keep followers informed about project milestones, upcoming events, and industry news, while also highlighting the collaborative efforts of our partners and stakeholders in advancing energy efficiency across Europe.

Table 1: Twitter Metrics

Twitter				
Followers	590			
No° of Posts	Impressions	Likes	Engagements	Retweets
80	15,043	381	1,093	88

The most popular Twitter post, about ENERGATE's participation at the #SmartEnergyCluster, has over 2,200 impressions.

Figure 1: ENERGATE most viewed twitter post

Figure 2: ENEREGATE top twitter posts

Figure 3: ENEREGATE project mentions from external sources

All Twitter posts include custom banners and tag ENEREGATE partners and/or relevant EU institutions, including [CINEA](#), [CINEA CLEAN ENERGY](#) and [LIFE Programme](#), as well as [some common hashtags such as #LIFEAmplifier and #LIFEProgramme](#). This strategy not only amplifies the message but also strengthens the relationship between the project and its audiences, contributing to a more interconnected and engaged community around the topics of clean energy and sustainable initiatives.

ENERGATE’s [LinkedIn page](#) serves as a professional hub for showcasing our commitment to advancing energy efficiency financing and sustainable building practices across Europe. Here, we connect with industry professionals, partners, and stakeholders, sharing in-depth articles, project updates, and insights into the latest trends and research in the field of energy efficiency. Our page is a space for fostering professional relationships, engaging with our community through thought leadership, and highlighting the achievements and milestones of the ENERGATE project.

Table 2: LinkedIn Metrics

LinkedIn			
Followers	530		
No° of Posts	Reactions	Shares	Impressions
100	1,265	139	28,198

Following a similar approach to the twitter posts, LinkedIn posts tag ENERGATE partners, [LIFE Programme](#), and [CINEA](#) official pages.

Figure 4: ENERGATE most viewed LinkedIn post

Figure 5: ENERGATE top LinkedIn posts

Figure 6: ENERGATE project mentions from external sources

Additionally, in December 2023, the [ENERGATE YouTube channel](#) was launched which features insightful content on our platform user interfaces for Building Owners, Implementors, Public Bodies and Financiers among other project-related information. This platform features

custom thumbnails and serves as a dynamic space for presenting the diverse aspects of the ENERGATE project, including its goals, achievements, and the impact on energy efficiency financing. The YouTube page will make all the information easier to grasp for our stakeholders, through animated and easy-to-follow videos.

Figure 7: ENERGATE Youtube thumbnails

Up until February 29th 2024, the ENERGATE Youtube profile counted a total of **145 views** and 4 videos uploaded. ENERGATE is also preparing to launch its 1st introductory video and a video about the 1st release of the ENERGATE platform on YouTube page.

After release, these videos were uploaded to the platform page ²in order to attract potential users and keep them engaged. By showcasing the breadth and depth of our offer, we aim to not only inform but also inspire our visitors. Videos intend to highlight the innovative solutions and success stories within the energy efficiency sector, demonstrating our commitment to sustainable development and industry-leading practices.

The details of the ENERGATE activity on social media can be found in Annex IV.

2.2.3. ENERGATE newsletters

By February 29th, 2024, ENERGATE had successfully issued two newsletters, utilising the Mailerlite platform for distribution. These newsletters were shared with 108 subscribers who gave their consent under GDPR and were also disseminated across our social media channels to enhance reach and engagement. The first newsletter, released in July 2023, introduced the project, its objectives, and highlighted the kick-off meeting, while the second one, issued in December 2023, highlighted the stakeholders' consultation material. Detailed descriptions are provided in Annex V.

The references to ENERGATE across external newsletters highlight the project's significant involvement and recognition within the energy sector, particularly in relation to energy

² https://energate-project.eu/energy_efficiency_marketplace

efficiency and smart energy transition. Overall, ENERGATE has been featured in 9 external newsletters (refer to the dissemination monitoring table in Annex VIII)

2.3. Communication and promotional package

As project partners are expected to attend events and dissemination sessions in representation of ENERGATE, a promotional package was developed as frontline support. This package includes a series of printable assets (brochure, poster, roll-up poster) and some banners for digital use (e.g. social media).

One pager

The One Pager for ENERGATE delineates the platform's goal of enhancing communication among various stakeholders involved in EE projects and actors in sustainable finance.

Key points include:

- **User Categories:** It elaborates on how the platform assists building owners and implementors by enabling them to report projects in a standardised manner, thus facilitating efficient interaction with investors. Furthermore, it illustrates how users can access data on other projects, best practices, and funding schemes.
- **Platform Stages:** The document outlines the workflow of the ENERGATE platform, structured into four primary stages: User Registration, Data Collection, Aggregation and Matchmaking, and Feedback and Validation. These stages are crafted to streamline the progression from project inception through to fruition, bolstering transparency and trust among participants.
- **ENERGATE Pilots:** It introduces the pilot cases that will test and validate the platform by providing data of energy efficiency projects in buildings that seek financing. These pilots represent both the supply and demand aspects of EE projects, ensuring that the platform is meticulously refined to meet the requirements of all market actors.

Additionally, the text emphasises the platform's contribution to supporting sustainable financing for the renovation of buildings, aiming to establish a dependable source of aggregated and precise information on EE projects for investment objectives. It concludes with an invitation to join the online community, reflecting the project's dedication to advancing a sustainable future in building renovations through innovative solutions,

The One Pager can be found on ENERGATEs' [website](#).

Presentation slide deck

Additionally, the promotional package includes a project presentation slide deck that is dynamic and iterative: built on initial needs identified by the partners and continuously updated in feedback loops. Currently, the document follows a modular approach, meaning partners can use it as is or extract and reuse individual slides.

The Presentation slide deck can be found on ENERGATEs' [website](#).

Brochure

It also is noteworthy that printable materials are available to partners in digital version. As printing is often a wasteful and environmentally unfriendly activity, partners are encouraged to

print only if and when they need the materials. At the time of this report, around 400 units of the brochure have been printed.

The brochure can be found on ENERGATEs' [website](#).

Roll-up banner

The Roll-up is segmented into four parts, each highlighting a different feature of the ENERGATE marketplace. Each feature is represented by a symbol and accompanied by a brief descriptor:

1. **Standardised facility:** A systematic approach to project facilitation and the use of established methods or criteria.
2. **Feedback loops:** Mechanism for measuring performance and gathering responses that could lead to continuous improvement.
3. **Project aggregation:** Consolidation of multiple energy efficiency projects into a single, more impactful investment opportunity.
4. **Business matchmaking:** The platforms role in connecting building owners, public bodies, implementors and financiers together.

Poster

The poster presents ENERGATEs' Key Achievements:

- The establishment of **5 pilot partnerships** that span across **6 EU countries**, which demonstrates ENERGATE's robust collaborative framework and its commitment to regional development.
- The initiation and progression of **up to 180 building renovation projects**, showcasing ENERGATE's capacity to scale operations and drive significant sectoral transformation.
- The realization of **up to 67 GWh/year in final energy savings**, reflecting ENERGATE's dedication to energy efficiency and the promotion of green initiatives.
- The significant reduction of **up to 23 tCO₂eq/year in greenhouse gas emissions**, affirming ENERGATE's pivotal role in the fight against climate change and support for EU's carbon neutrality goals.
- The generation of **up to 53 million euros in triggered investments**, highlighting the economic impact and investor confidence that ENERGATE has cultivated within the energy sector. The poster can be found on ENERGATEs' [website](#).

All the elements of the promotional package are in the ANNEX VI of this document.

2.4. Complementary dissemination assets

While the promotional package supports a broader communication of the project, the dissemination of ENERGATE outputs requires the development of custom, complementary, assets. For this reason, submitted deliverables – as well as conclusions and outcomes of research and ENERGATE events – inspired complementary dissemination assets such as reports, briefs, and fact sheets.

It is also noteworthy that assets are not being produced only when final outputs are available; instead, focus is also on disseminating the research process of ENERGATE. For this reason,

some contextual assets are also available, namely describing user profiles for the platform and key features of the marketplace.

As partners flagged new needs while developing their activities, supporting visual assets were also designed. These assets include maps, pilot integration schemes, cooperation figures, and greeting cards – but the list will likely expand with time as new requirements arise.

Due to their supporting nature, complementary dissemination assets are hard to foresee accurately, despite being somewhat expected. For that reason, they are – and will continue being – approached by the dissemination strategy in a flexible and iterative manner, going beyond what is described in the Grant Agreement. An example of this approach are the 4 videos produced for the platform user profiles.

An overview of the complementary dissemination assets already available is provided in ANNEX VII.

2.5. Scientific publications

A total of nine scientific publications have been released during the first 12 months of the project ENERATE and are currently at different stages of acceptance (refer to Annex IX). As these publications were inspired by project outputs, more scientific work is expected in the upcoming months following the natural development of project activities.

All scientific publications are monitored collaboratively by partners in a dissemination monitoring file shared in the project drive. The latest version of this file is transposed to ANNEX VIII.

Additionally, to the already published papers, others are to be published or submitted soon. An overview of the publication plan can be found in Annex IX.

2.6. Events

Since it began, ENERATE has been featured in **13 events**. However, more events are already being prepared.

Some future events include:

1. The [EMCEI conference](#), 15-18 May 2024.
2. [ENERATE-InEEExS-FORTESIE joint webinar](#) (within the framework of Sustainable Energy Days): From Tech to Transformation: Accelerating Building Energy Efficiency through ICT Solutions on May 16.
3. ENERATE Regional Training Workshop in Riga, 29th May 2024.
4. [EURO 2024](#) in Copenhagen, 30 June – 3 July 2024.
5. [IISA 2024](#) - 4th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector in Chania, 17-19 July 2024.

Events are collaboratively tracked in the shared monitoring file transposed to ANNEX VIII.

Figure 8: ENEREGATEs' participation in various events

2.6.1. Project-branded events

The ENEREGATE consortium has organised one event in the first months of the project, targeting local stakeholders in Spain. In this regional workshop, participants were presented a preliminary overview of the ENEREGATE marketplace and asked to provide feedback on it. There was also a discussion panel on the challenges of financing energy efficiency projects for buildings. Real estate experts, project implementors, and policy makers took active part in the discussion.

As the project progresses, more regional events are expected – such as the second regional public event, to happen in Riga (Latvia) in May 2024.

Additionally, ENEREGATE is preparing a session for the European Sustainable Energy Days, which will focus on the implementation gaps of the new regulations for energy efficiency in buildings.

2.6.2. External events

Complementary to its self-organised events, ENEREGATE has been featured in external events. Some of these events are institutionally organised by project partners (e.g. REHVA Brussels Summit, GGGI Week); others are organised by institutions external to the consortium (e.g. Built4People).

2.7. Synergies with other relevant EU initiatives

The ENEREGATE project is currently an active member of the the Smart Energy Cluster (21 projects). Complementarily, the consortium builds bi-lateral partnerships with relevant EU-funded projects, such as EN-TRACK, MATRYCS, SMAFIN, InEEsS, and FORTESIE.

Specifically, ENERGATE made a joint article³ with MATRYCS H2020, to incentivise energy efficiency in the building sector.

Additionally, to the synergies that ENERGATE conducted in terms of dissemination and communication activities, there were also meetings organised with other projects for technical exchange. Further details on these meetings will be provided in D6.3 Joint Activities with Other Projects and Initiatives.

Besides attending (and organising) several meetings with partner projects, ENERGATE has also participated in joint activities, such as:

- [SMAFIN National Roundtable Meeting](#)
- International workshop at : [14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications \(2023\)](#),

Additionally, other clustering events are being prepared: a cluster session with [InEExS](#) and [FORTESIE](#) projects on European Sustainable Energy Days (work in progress), and a [joint webinar](#) with the EN-TRACK project. ENERGATE will also co-organise a workshop at [IISA 2024](#): “4th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector⁴”, along with the EU projects DigiBUILD, DEDALUS, Enpower, Crete Valley, Hedge – IoT and METABUILD.

Further details on synergies will be provided in D6.3 Joint Activities with Other Projects and Initiatives.

³ <https://energate-project.eu/MATRYCS-and-ENERGATE-projects-joining-forces-to-incentivise-energy-efficiency-in-the-building-sector>

⁴ <https://energate-project.eu/ENERGATE-at-IISA-2024>

3. Performance assessment

The status of ENERGATEs' performance based on the KPI's are presented below. ENERGATE has managed to already achieve most of them, with only one underachievement and some still in progress.

Table 3: Current status of KPI achievement

Activity	KPI	Achieved	Progress status
Project identity	Release on M2	Released on M2	Achieved
Website	5,000 unique visitors /year	3,616	Underachieved
	15% returning visitors	20%	Achieved
Dedicated project page on beneficiaries' websites	12 pages (1 per partner)	11 pages (+1 in progress)	In progress
Social media	30 posts	178	Achieved
Newsletter	5 newsletters	2	In progress
Brochure	200 downloads per year	335 views	Achieved
	1.000 prints distributed	400	In progress
One pager	Distribution in events and online presentation	Distributed at the stakeholder consultation training	Achieved
Infographics and fact sheets	Assets for WP2 reports	Assets produced for D2.1, D2.2, and D2.3	Achieved
Scientific papers	2 papers in journals	2 in progress	In progress
	2 conference papers	6 conference papers	Achieved
Media pieces	3 articles per partner	16 total (3 from SCN, 3 from IEECP, 4 from REHVA, 1 from LDK, 1 from RPR, 4 from NTUA)	In progress
	1,000 total reads	958	In progress
	10 references in relevant media	60 references	Achieved
Clustering activities	Clustering via website, social media and joint	54 joint activities	Achieved

	development of activities		
Events	4 regional training workshops	1 regional training workshop organised 1 under preparation	In progress
	1 final event	NA	NA
Activities Beyond the Grant Agreement	4 YouTube videos about Public Bodies, Implementors, Financiers and Building Owners.		

4. Conclusions and next steps

The dissemination and communication activities outlined in the ENERGATE project have been systematically executed according to the strategic plan detailed in the 1st version of the ENERGATE Dissemination and Communication Strategy. Covering the period from January 2023 to February 2024, this document reflects on the extensive efforts undertaken to promote the Energy Efficiency Aggregation Platform for Sustainable Investments, underscoring significant achievements, and setting the stage for future objectives.

ENERGATE has been proactive in deploying a comprehensive suite of communication tools and platforms, demonstrating adaptability and innovation beyond the initial Grant Agreement. From the creation of a distinct visual identity to extensive digital outreach via the project website and social media, ENERGATE has established a formidable online presence. The project's adept use of digital tools has not only enhanced visibility among target audiences but has also facilitated engagement with key stakeholders across the energy efficiency spectrum.

Key accomplishments include the surpassing of several targets, such as the number of social media posts, engagement metrics, and the creation of diverse communication materials like brochures, infographics, and scientific publications. Particularly noteworthy is the project's success in fostering synergies with relevant EU initiatives, enhancing the dissemination reach and impact.

However, the path was not without its challenges. Some KPIs are in progress and need more effort, yet strategic adjustments and targeted actions have been put in place to address these issues effectively. The introduction of stretch goals for certain activities reflects the project's dynamic approach to maximizing its dissemination and communication potential in its remaining duration. More details to come in D7.4 Dissemination and Communication Strategy - final version.

As ENERGATE moves forward, the updated KPIs and the strategic emphasis on digital dissemination, coupled with continued engagement in scientific and event-driven outreach, signal a robust framework for promoting the project's objectives and outcomes. The comprehensive performance assessment underpins a strategic review that not only acknowledges the successes to date but also keenly identifies areas for improvement and expansion.

ENERGATE Upcoming activities include:

- ENERGATE Co-organisation of the “4th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector” at the IISA 2024 conference in December in Crete, Greece, along with the sister projects DigiBUILD, DEDALUS EU, Enpower, Crete Valley, Hedge-IoT, METABUILD, and the ENERGATE Project.
- Organisation of the ENERGATE 2nd Regional Training Workshop in Riga, May 29, 2024.
- Co-organisation of the webinar “From Tech to Transformation: Accelerating Building Energy Efficiency through ICT Solutions” in collaboration with ENERGATE, InEEoS and FORTESIE within the framework of the Sustainable Energy Days, May 16, 2024.
- Development of dissemination material for the 1st Official release of the platform (Video Tutorials, Communication packages).
- Participation on the #SmartEnergyCluster 2nd Collaboration Workshop on April 8, 2024.
- Continuous updates on the dissemination and communication material based on the projects' stages (brochure, banner, poster, roll-up, etc.)

- Publications:
 - Papapostolou, A., Andreoulaki, I., Kotrogiannis, V., Psarras, J. (2024). Utilising Decision-Making methods and online tools to accelerate sustainable renovation investments: Insights from a stakeholder engagement approach. In 2024 33rd EURO Conference - accepted
 - Andreoulaki, I., Papapostolou, A., Kotrogiannis, V., Marinakis, V. (2024). Promoting retrofitting projects in buildings: the designing steps of an online marketplace. In 2024 6th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI) – accepted
 - Submission of a paper in the Special Issue on Computing, Engineering and Multidisciplinary Sciences - Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal
 - Submission of a paper for the 4th International Workshop on Big Data Analytics in the Energy | IISA 2024

Annex I | Visual identity

Figure 9: Project logo versions

Figure 10: Brand manual (extracts)

Annex II | Project website

The "[About](#)" page of the ENERGate project details its aims, methodologies, contributions, pilot programs, and the team behind it. It emphasises the project's objectives towards energy efficiency, the approach taken to achieve these goals, how the project contributes to the broader energy sector, details about pilot sites where the project's concepts are tested, and information about the consortium of partners involved. This page also links to sections for news, events, a library of results and publications, communication materials, and how to contact the project team. The page has a total of **451 views**.

Figure 11: ENERGate website – Home page

The "[News & Events](#)" page provides updates and insights on various activities and milestones associated with the project. It features sections for news, events, and blog posts, offering a comprehensive overview of the project's progress, upcoming events, and significant achievements. Each entry includes a brief summary and a link for more detailed information, ensuring visitors are well-informed about the latest developments in the ENERGate project. So far, **32 news**, events and blog items have been officially published through the ENERGate platform and has **783 views**.

Figure 12: ENEREGATE website – News & Events

The "[Results](#)" section of the ENEREGATE project website details various deliverables and reports produced throughout the project's lifecycle. It includes comprehensive analyses on topics like building renovation financing typologies, specifications for project entries, user profiles, stakeholder engagement plans, insights from energy efficiency workshops and dissemination and awareness creation. Each entry provides a summary of the report's aims, methodologies, and findings, designed to support the development, deployment, and validation of the ENEREGATE platform, as well as stakeholder engagement and sustainability efforts. The Results page has **278 views**.

Figure 13: ENEREGATE website – Results

The "[Scientific Publications](#)" section showcases academic papers related to the project's objectives and findings. These publications cover topics like accelerating building renovation rates in Europe, sustainable investment strategies in the building sector, building typologies to support renovation investments, and the architecture of the ENEREGATE system as an energy efficiency marketplace for buildings. Each publication provides insights into the challenges and solutions for enhancing energy efficiency and sustainability within the built environment, reflecting the project's contribution to academic and practical knowledge in the field. This page has **197 views**.

Figure 14: ENERGate website – Scientific Publications

The "[Newsletters](#)" section of the ENERGate project website includes editions of the ENERGate Newsletter and press releases. These publications provide updates on the project's progress, insights into energy efficiency topics, summaries of events like the GGGI Week 2023, and highlights of ENERGate's contributions to the European marketplace for energy efficiency. It has a total of **364 views**.

Figure 15: ENERGate website – Newsletters

The "[Communication Material](#)" offers a collection of promotional and informational resources. This includes the ENERGate Brand Manual, brochure, poster, roll-up, and media like factsheets and infographics detailing financing typologies for building renovation, use cases for the Energy Efficiency Marketplace, key takeaways from training workshops, and expert talks at the REHVA Brussels Summit. These materials are designed to effectively

communicate the project's scope, objectives, and insights to a wider audience. So far, it has **328 page views**.

Figure 16: ENERDATE website – Communication Material

The "[Synergies](#)" page highlights collaborations with other projects and initiatives aiming to enhance energy efficiency, data analytics, and smart energy management across various sectors. It outlines the objectives, strategies, and outcomes of partnerships with initiatives like BD4NRG, MATRYCS, I-ENERGY, and several others. These collaborations are designed to leverage big data, AI, and innovative technologies to promote sustainable energy usage and efficiency at multiple levels, from individual buildings to broader energy communities. ENERDATE is under the **#SmartEnergyCluster Collaboration**, which counts more than 20 projects, and it continues to grow rapidly. It has **121 views**.

Figure 17: ENERDATE website – Synergies

The "[Contact](#)" section provides contact details for project inquiries. It lists the ENERDATE Project Manager, Katerina Papapostolou, with her role, affiliation to the National Technical University of Athens, and contact information. Additionally, it mentions the ENERDATE Dissemination Leader, Marta Maia, her role as a Communication Expert, affiliation with IEECP, and contact details. This page facilitates communication with the project's key personnel for stakeholders and interested parties interested in reaching out to ENERDATE's contact e-mail for any queries they may have. The page has **101 views**.

Figure 18: ENEREGATE website – Contact

Last but not least, one of the most important pages of the ENEREGATEs’ website, the [Energy Efficiency Marketplace](#), which describes the upcoming platform aimed at connecting stakeholders in the energy efficiency sector. This includes Building Owners (Public Bodies and Private Owners), Implementors, and Financiers. The page highlights the importance of meeting the needs of various user profiles within the energy efficiency community and includes more information and resources, such as user videos, to better understand the platform's potential impact. The testing phase will be until June 2024, and after the public release of the platform will follow. This page is the connection between the ENEREGATE website and the soon to be release platform. So far, it has **378 views**.

Figure 19: ENEREGATE website – Energy Efficiency Marketplace

Annex III | Network of partner's webpages

Table 4: ENERGATE dedicated webpages

Partner	Webpage link
NTUA	https://www.epu.ntua.gr/ENERGATE
IEECP	https://ieecp.org/projects/ENERGATE/
REHVA	https://www.rehva.eu/eu-projects/project/ENERGATE
ENERBRAIN	https://www.enerbrain.com/en/about-us/research-and-development/
Sustainable City	https://www.sustainable-city.gr/projects-list/ENERGATE
Global Green Growth Institute	https://gggi.org/project/hu06-ENERGATE-energy-efficiency-aggregation-platform-for-sustainable-investments/
Riga planning Region	https://rpr.gov.lv/project/ENERGATE/
Enersave Capital	https://www.enersavecap.com/initiatives
COMMUTY	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/wearecommuty/about/</p> <p>COMMUTY is undergoing a significant rebranding process from the parent company, Fluxus Ventures, which will require some time to complete. Currently, COMMUTY is in the process of finalising its dedicated project webpage. In the meantime, a compensatory strategy has been in place: an ENERGATE reference was placed in the LinkedIn page of COMMUTY as a remedy action until the official website will be ready to host the ENERGATE page.</p>
LDK Consultants	https://www.ldk.gr/component/ldkprojects/?view=project&id=723-ENERGATE-project-energy-efficiency-aggregation-platform-for-sustainable-investments&Itemid=279&cid=19
GREENESCO	https://www.greenesco.gr/services/ENERGATE/
Flexiwatt	http://flexiwatt.io/projects.html

Figure 20: ENER GATE partners webpages

Annex IV | Social media monitoring table

Table 5: ENERGATE social media posts (LinkedIn)

A/A	LinkedIn Posts	Impressions	Reposts	Reactions
1	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7024341686319230976	1464	17	54
2	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7024721923112603648	1985	1	75
3	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7042100777837862912	207	0	0
4	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7049667240396230657	777	10	23
5	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7050052057440956416	333	4	19
6	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7051136384996151296	344	3	16
7	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7051851128723935232	277	2	17
8	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7054386361037955074	340	1	21
9	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7055145279624294402	231	0	12
10	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7056219467239874560	205	0	11
11	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7056594661519278080	236	0	22
12	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7056918618629963776	157	0	10
13	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057288660999692288	190	4	20
14	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057376516648615936	147	0	9
15	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7057645753225146368	203	2	18
16	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059096988193046528	220	0	17
17	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059483043756937217	273	5	14
18	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7059814904005898240	157	1	13
19	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7060210342869557248	370	3	18
20	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061301242228056064	262	2	14
21	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7061624422213763072	159	1	10

A/A	LinkedIn Posts	Impressions	Reposts	Reactions
22	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062034833857757184	110	1	10
23	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062404260277161984	278	2	10
24	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7062739264035299329	206	0	11
25	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7063847020440039424	297	0	14
26	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7064158917546680320	195	1	12
27	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7064907402822791169	95	0	0
28	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7066751032051064833	221	0	16
29	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067473210107117568	102	0	0
30	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7067478602774122496	432	0	15
31	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072143378322194434	90	0	2
32	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7072144085821571072	276	2	13
33	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7073940079374667776	243	2	11
34	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7074766049237188609	129	0	8
35	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7075119607182671872	375	0	19
36	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7077210987178696704	42	0	0
37	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7080186457268625410	150	0	10
38	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7080217099901517825	186	0	12
39	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7084522925457911808	55	0	0
40	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7085583890630754304	433	3	23
41	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7085617318566801408	255	0	12
42	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7087090063934709761	390	0	14
43	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7087412384016867328	252	3	15

A/A	LinkedIn Posts	Impressions	Reposts	Reactions
44	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7088090452217729025	257	11	16
45	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7088167809104437248	184	3	13
46	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7089211399599456256	200	1	9
47	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7089591496441552896	165	0	3
48	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7089949642527772672	72	0	0
49	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7097616486814351362	76	0	0
50	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7099348554279743489	157	0	7
51	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7104393174109855744	814	5	25
52	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7104604594311208960	80	0	0
53	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7105512377340559362	506	2	28
54	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7106947925074731008	127	0	10
55	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ENERGATE-project_ENERGATEabreu-ENERGATEabreu-commuty-activity-7112056638718550016-Ak3A	610	8	20
56	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7112393594388254720	192	2	6
57	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7112754368608710656	131	1	8
58	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ENERGATE-project_ENERGATEabreu-buildingowner-implementor-activity-7113215176283217920-Rakl	335	3	17
59	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7113241563266187266	203	4	12
60	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7113482233386065920	480	6	20
61	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7114937604956991489	257	0	13
62	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7114953588522557440	786	4	29
63	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/uli-spain_c-c-esg-ugcPost-7114515708146823169-OVIK	438	4	16

A/A	LinkedIn Posts	Impressions	Reposts	Reactions
64	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7117071611874177024	58	0	2
65	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ieecp_policy-roundtable-make-energy-efficiency-activity-7117420985179328512-9ael	78	0	3
66	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7117849340366270464	84	1	5
67	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7118495840477847552	171	2	10
68	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120023793145671680	481	4	16
69	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120347858137993217		5	16
70	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7120748621406347264	72	0	2
71	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122169309438619648	93	0	3
72	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122596042847531010		3	11
73	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7122926776233701376	201	1	5
74	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7123671805034119169	310	2	12
75	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7126112492526665728	205	0	8
76	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ENERGATE-project_rehvabrusselssummit-ENERGATEabreu-lifeamplifier-activity-7128383776971251712-O_NN	334	2	15
77	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7128678750438735873		2	15
78	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130161360901988353	225	1	3
79	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7130507614265692160	145	1	11
80	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7132263692431151104	5	0	3
81	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133039900798443520	155	0	10
82	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133431069361459201	162	2	15
83	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7133801802386264064	143	2	4
84	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135268793252990978	11	0	3

A/A	LinkedIn Posts	Impressions	Reposts	Reactions
85	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7135980299565359104	261	4	28
86	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7138497983255416832	214	3	20
87	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7142538886437658624	446	0	17
88	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7143609269748248578	480	4	13
89	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7143910588526632961	270	1	12
90	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7150476261625159681	504	6	25
91	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7155519192669052928	163	2	8
92	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7157696075988975617	238	2	9
93	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7158116160524173312	293	3	13

Figure 21: ENERGATE LinkedIn analytics based on Job Function

Figure 22: ENERGate LinkedIn analytics based on Industry

Table 6: ENERGate social media posts (Twitter)

A/A	Twitter (X) Posts	Impressions	Retweets	Likes
1	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1651872753643929600	61	0	3
2	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1651610773326647300	98	1	4
3	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1651522357079539712	107	1	4
4	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1651149697086631936	91	0	4
5	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1650814064975544321	123	1	6
6	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1650437944639987712	102	0	5
7	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1649410810152730624	63	0	4
8	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1648619830948384768	109	0	4
9	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1646088494685515777	286	1	3
10	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1645396999653425152	305	4	6
11	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1644286052901724160	164	2	6

A/A	Twitter (X) Posts	Impressions	Retweets	Likes
12	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1643892759919468544	437	5	8
13	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1661711993793806337	149	5	6
14	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1661354135428513792	51	0	4
15	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1660985447290482689	44	0	3
16	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1658392431161647106	77	0	3
17	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1658078161509163009	352	3	5
18	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1656969524380401665	55	0	3
19	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1656645467726401536	114	0	5
20	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1656269123209293824	88	0	3
21	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1655860357854818304	170	2	6
22	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1655535524893929473	70	0	3
23	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1654441465030778882	68	0	3
24	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1654049095907000320	108	0	5
25	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1653710160966164481	183	3	7
26	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1653338005514473477	83	0	3
27	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1674450264676343809	129	0	6
28	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1674419516183560193	148	1	6
29	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1669355236195205120	2192	2	13
30	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1669000380699537408	93	1	3
31	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1668174367627399169	160	4	4
32	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1666744879702065161	174	3	8
33	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/168344447969787904	98	0	7
34	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1682399648550461441	32	0	2
35	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1682324747181338624	236	5	4
36	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1681651606339682304	136	1	5

A/A	Twitter (X) Posts	Impressions	Retweets	Likes
37	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1681324914857345025	571	2	4
38	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1679852028271493121	70	0	3
39	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1679814576731242496	147	2	5
40	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1693582402747068755	87	0	3
41	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1698627522009653338	227	1	11
42	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1699750025444679716	83	2	4
43	https://twitter.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1701182212446556184	73	0	3
44	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1706277574244978772?s=20	327	4	3
45	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1706626290466361392?s=20	68	0	3
46	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1706987779349946573?s=20	70	0	3
47	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1707447414657802467?s=20	107	1	4
48	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1707475180010803372?s=20	179	2	5
49	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1707715408042566085?s=20	495	2	7
50	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1709170627456692490?s=20	422	2	1
51	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1711303919953932378?s=20	104	0	3
52	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1714255218257346968?s=20	207	4	12
53	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1714982095318102470?s=20	50	0	1
54	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1716403372385845295?s=20	58	0	1
55	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1717155899289014388?s=20	70	0	4
56	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1717804173557641560?s=20	56	0	5
57	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1720345934570107247?s=20	71	0	2

A/A	Twitter (X) Posts	Impressions	Retweets	Likes
58	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1722615355091415297?s=20	85	0	4
59	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1724394300673327549?s=20	66	0	3
60	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1724741459532800116?s=20	73	0	5
61	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1727275318694834665?s=20	59	1	4
62	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1727663090429239618?s=20	62	0	3
63	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1729503026396696688?s=20	68	0	3
64	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1730212955810128052?s=20	77	0	4
65	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1732730618566389884?s=20	108	0	4
66	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1737848768924667936?s=20	123	3	7
67	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1738155916288254231?s=20	52	0	0
68	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1744711035276198153?s=20	40	0	1
69	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1749755090477449463?s=20	83	0	5
70	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1751928694187176058?s=20	144	3	6
71	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1752349327328977159?s=20	81	0	6
72	https://x.com/ENERGATE_eu/status/1752972535514231175?s=20	408	3	5

Annex V | ENEREGATE newsletters

Figure 23: ENEREGATE 1st Newsletter

The [1st Newsletter, Issue in July 2023](#), reached 53 stakeholders.. The Newsletter covered many topics including:

1. **Introduction of ENEREGATE:** The campaign kicks off with the announcement of the ENEREGATE project, which aims to provide a smart energy marketplace for sustainable investments in buildings. This marketplace will be facilitated through an ICT-based platform designed to mobilise and accelerate the creation of credible project pipelines compatible with National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs), and to facilitate financial closure and project implementation.
2. **ENEREGATE Website Launch:** It mentions the launch of the [official ENEREGATE website](#) in April 2023, inviting readers to visit the site to learn more about the project's vision.
3. **Smart Energy Cluster Participation:** ENEREGATE's involvement in the Smart Energy Cluster is highlighted, emphasising the collaborative effort of 19 projects to support the smart energy transition by developing new business models and concepts.
4. **Financing Typologies for Building Renovation:** A [brief on financing typologies for building renovation](#) is discussed, based on a review of 83 publications and 65 case studies across 18 European countries. This document aims to explore the most relevant financing typologies identified for the ENEREGATE project.
5. **Upcoming and Past Events:** Various ENEREGATE-related events, including the [1st ENEREGATE Regional Training Workshop in Madrid](#), participation in the [REHVA Brussels Summit 2023](#), and highlights from past events like the [14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications \(IISA 2023\)](#), among others.
6. **Publications and Reports:** Information on ENEREGATE's publications and reports, including topics on [financing typologies for building renovation](#), stakeholder engagement plans, and the dissemination & communication strategy.
7. **Collaborative Projects and Initiatives:** ENEREGATE's participation in various collaborative events and projects, such as the EU Projects Clustering event "Smart Energy Services" and workshops aimed at fostering energy efficiency renovation processes.
8. **Links to More Information:** Several links are provided for readers who wish to delve deeper into ENEREGATE's social media channels.

Figure 24: ENEREGATE 2nd Newsletter

The 2nd Newsletter, Issue in December 2023, reached 88 stakeholders. The 2nd Newsletter covered many topics, including:

1. **Stakeholder Consultation for Future Shaping:** ENEREGATE invites stakeholders to engage in a consultation process to shape the future of sustainable financing in buildings. This process is crucial for co-creating the platform, fostering meaningful dialogue, and ensuring the platform's relevance and effectiveness in meeting the community's needs.
2. **Participation and Co-Creation Invitation:** Stakeholders are encouraged to participate in the dialogue and contribute to the platform's development. The consultation seeks to gather insights and feedback to refine the platform, with an emphasis on creating a sustainable and efficient built environment. Stakeholders participating in the consultation will gain early access to the platform, influence its features, and have their logos featured as supportive partners.
3. **Insights from REHVA Expert Talk:** [Key takeaways](#) from the ENEREGATE participation in the REHVA Expert Talk highlight the challenges of financing building renovations due to low trust and the critical role of standardization in achieving EU renovation objectives. These insights are instrumental in guiding the platform's development to address these challenges.
4. **Feedback from Regional Training Workshop in Madrid:** The ENEREGATE project summarised feedback from financial stakeholders during a regional workshop in Madrid, focusing on what investors seek in energy efficiency projects. This feedback is vital for tailoring the platform to meet investor expectations and project needs.
5. **Survey Insights on Energy Efficiency Needs:** [A survey](#) conducted during the Madrid workshop revealed the needs of project developers, energy consultants, and financiers regarding energy efficiency platforms. These insights are crucial for ensuring the ENEREGATE platform aligns with the needs of its users.
6. **Collaboration with MATRYCS:** The [ENEREGATE project is joining forces with the MATRYCS H2020 project](#) to enhance energy efficiency in buildings. This collaboration aims to improve building performance and support energy efficiency investments, demonstrating the project's commitment to leveraging synergies for greater impact. Also past events were mentioned, including The 1st Regional Training Workshop,

REHVA Brussels Summit 2023, 2nd ENERGATE Project Meeting, ENERGATE at Global Green Growth Week and ENERGATE at BIGG Final Event.

7. **Upcoming Regional Training Workshop in Riga and Past Events:** The announcement of the 2nd Regional Training Workshop in Riga, planned for Spring – Summer 2024, aims to introduce stakeholders to the newly launched ENERGATE Energy Efficiency Marketplace. This event will be a pivotal moment for engaging with stakeholders and showcasing the platform's capabilities.
8. **#SmartEnergyCluster News:** Updates from the #SmartEnergyCluster, initiated by the [InEExS project](#), highlight the dynamic community's efforts to advance energy-related projects. The inclusion of new members and the focus on collaboration and innovation underscore the cluster's role in fostering a supportive ecosystem for energy efficiency initiatives.
9. **Links to More Information:** Several links are provided for readers who wish to delve deeper into ENERGATEs' social media channels.

ENERGATE
ENERGY EFFICIENCY MARKETPLACE

Building renovation investments: easy, predictable, and risk-weighted

- Large and standardised project development facility
- Asset bundling scaled investment
- Feedback loops to measure the impact of the platform
- Matching opportunities with investors
- Business matchmaking, quality assessments, and rankings

5 PILOTS PARTNERS IN 6 EU COUNTRIES

UP TO **180** BUILDING RENOVATION PROJECTS

UP TO **132** FINAL ENERGY SAVINGS GWh/year

UP TO **171** GHG EMISSIONS SAVED tCO₂eq/year

UP TO **314** TRIGGERED INVESTMENTS Million Euros

How?

STAGE 1 | FETCH
Collect structured information about projects. Ensuring that technical and commercial data is appropriate.

STAGE 2 | PROCESS
Identification of similarities between projects and investors KPIs which might result in bundles.

STAGE 3 | DELIVER
Follow up on projects, validation of M&V methodologies, and definition of relevant KPIs.

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EPU | IEEP | flexiwatt | SUSTAINABLE CITY | GREENESCO | enerbrain | EnerSaveCapital | community | LDK CONSULTANTS

Figure 28: ENERGATE poster

Figure 29: ENERGATE roll-up poster

Annex VII | Complementary dissemination assets

Figure 30: Complementary assets: support visuals

Figure 31: ENERGATE Christmas greetings card

Figure 32: Factsheets on financing typologies for building renovations

Figure 33: Brief on financing typologies for building renovation

Figure 34: Report on energy efficiency in buildings

Figure 35: Report on user profiles for the ENERGATE platform

Figure 36: Custom icons for ENERGATE website

Annex VIII | Dissemination monitoring tables

Table 7: ENERGATE dissemination monitoring table (Events)

#	Date	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof	Comments
1	2023-04-25	EU Project Clustering event: Smart Energy Services	Online	Webinar Clustering activity: YES	Link	ENERGATE participated to explore potential synergies with other EU projects and ideas. Several EU-funded projects presented their methodologies towards scaling up knowledge to secure smart energy services in unleash the energy efficiency and flexibility potential of European buildings. The event was disseminated through social media posts.
2	2023-05-03	3rd SMAFIN National Roundtable Meeting	Athens, Greece	Panel-discussion Clustering activity: YES	Link	ENERGATE, represented by Project Manager Katerina Papapostolou, participated in a roundtable discussion on integrating the ENERGATE platform into an OSS (Open Source Software) framework. The event was disseminated through social media posts.
3	2023-04-06	ENERGATE project presentation to Riga City Development Department	Riga, Latvia	Workshop	Link	During the Workshop ENERGATE project was presented, highlighting the objectives and outcomes of energy efficiency investment platform and its intention to foster energy efficiency renovation processes that will be achieved through pooling financial instruments and linking building owners and energy service companies. The event was disseminated through ENERGATEs' website and social media posts.
4	2023-06-30	9th International Symposium and 31st National Conference on Operational Research	Athens, Greece	Conference	Link	ENERGATE participated at the conference and 2 papers related to project's advances were presented: "Sustainable investments in the building sector: A critical review of financing tools and methods" by Andreoulaki Ioanna,

#	Date	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof	Comments
						<p>Papapostolou Aikaterini, Karakosta Charikleia, Mexis Filippou Dimitrios, Psarras John</p> <p>"Investigating a Building Typology for Supporting Renovation Investments" by Papapostolou Aikaterini, Andreoulaki Ioanna, Touloumis Konstantinos, Kapsalis Panagiotis, Psarras John</p>
5	2023-07-11	14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications (IISA 2023)ENERGATE	Chania, Greece	Workshop Clustering activity: YES	Link	<p>ENERGATE project participated in the 14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications (IISA 2023), which took place on July 10 – 12, 2023, technically co-sponsored by IEEE, the University of Piraeus and the University of Thessaly. The event was disseminated through ENERGATE's website and social media posts.</p> <p>A paper was presented with the title: "An Energy Efficiency Marketplace for Buildings: The ENERGATE System Architecture" by Panagiotis Kapsalis, Aikaterini Papapostolou, Konstantinos Touloumis, Ioanna Andreoulaki, Zoi Mylona, Haris Doukas</p>
6	2023-10-10	ENERGATE Workshop Madrid	Madrid, Hybrid	Workshop	Link	<p>The 1st Regional Workshop of the ENERGATE project "Energy efficiency, from financing to implementation" was held on the 28 September 2023 (18:00 Local time) at Círculo de Bellas Artes, in Madrid. The event was co-organised by ENERGATE Spanish partners COMMUTY and the Urban Land Institute Spain. The workshop was disseminated through social media posts and from ENERGATE's website.</p>
7	2023-10-10	Built4People partnership – Stakeholders Forum Annual event	Online	Webinar Clustering activity: YES	Link	<p>ENERGATE participated at the Stakeholders Forum, where the project showed interest in collaborating with different projects in the energy efficiency sector. The event was disseminated through social media posts.</p>

#	Date	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof	Comments
8	2023-10-23	ENERGATE's participation at GGGI Week	Online	Conference	Link	ENERGATE participated in the Session "Research Policy Interface to Upscale Multi-Level Climate Action" through the presentation " Facilitating the creation of an effective, ICT-enabled, energy efficiency marketplace " which was delivered by NTUA on the 27th of October from 9.00 until 10.00 am CET, which had 50 participants. This event was disseminated through social media posts and at ENERGATE's website.
9	2023-11-13	REHVA Brussels Summit 2023	Maison des Associations Internationales Rue Washington 40, 1050 Brussels, Belgium	Conference	Link	ENERGATE participated in the REHVA Brussels Summit on the 13-14 November 2023. The summit is a significant gathering of industry experts, policymakers, and professionals, set to discuss the latest in sustainable buildings, with a theme centered on "Indoor Environmental Quality, Digitalization, and Skills in the Decarbonization of Buildings." The event was disseminated through social media posts and at ENERGATE's website. ENERGATE participated at the MODERATE workshop as well
10	2023-11-24	Buildspace webinar	Online	Education and training events Clustering activity: YES	Link	ENERGATE participated at the first co-creation session laid the foundation for this collaborative journey, and the upcoming second session is a pivotal step forward. This session presented the project's progress and services workflow, ensuring all stakeholders are well-informed about the current status and future direction.
11	27/12/2023	EN-TRACK and eQuad: Integrated Solutions to Improve Your Building Portfolio	Online	Webinar Clustering activity: YES	Link	ENERGATE was invited to participated in the EN-TRACK and EQuad joint event. EN-TRACK is a one-stop shop platform with standardized data related to the energy efficiency performance of public and private building stock, enabling interoperability with most currently active databases and tools. This leads to an unambiguous data exchange-based services ecosystem with low transactional costs.

#	Date	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof	Comments
						eQuad helps European energy efficiency project managers (ESCOs, engineering firms, and construction companies) access appropriate project finance while lowering upfront due diligence costs for investors.
12	07/03/2024	ENERGATE & EN-TRACK Joint Webinar	Online	Webinar Clustering activity: YES	Link	"Innovative Pathways: EN-TRACK & ENERGATE Projects' Solutions for Enhanced Building Renovations." This online event took place on 12 March from 15:00 to 16:00 CET, is aimed at addressing the critical need for energy efficiency renovations within the building sector.
13	13/03/2024	8th General Assembly of Sustainable Cities Network	Wyndham Grand Hotel, Athens, Greece	Group Discussion	Link	Team members of the European Projects division, who presented the most significant ongoing and completed European projects of the Network. Specifically, emphasis was placed on the projects HyPro4ST, Living Streets, SETOFF, DECIDO, DATABUILD, ENERGATE, RISKADAPT, POWERPOOR, and POWERYOUTH.

Table 8: ENERGATE dissemination monitoring table (except events)

#	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof
1	ENERGATE webpage	REHVA Website	Website	Link
2	ENERGATE KoM	LDK website	Press release	Link
3	ENERGATE webpage	EPU website	Website	Link
4	ENERGATE kick off meeting	REHVA website	Press release	Link
5	Energy Efficiency: building a barrier-free marketplace for all	IEECP Website	Press release	Link
6	Reference to ENERGATE in the newsletter	IEECP Newsletter	Newsletter	Link
7	ENERGATE kick off meeting	SCN Website	Press release	Link
8	ENERGATE webpage	SCN Website	Website	Link

#	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof
9	Reference to ENEREGATE in the newsletter	IIECP newsletter	Newsletter	Link
10	Integrating Existing Knowledge to Accelerate Buildings Renovation Rates in Europe	ICDSST 2023, Springer	Scientific Publication	Link
11	ENEREGATE webpage	LDK website	Website	Link
12	ENEREGATE webpage	Flexiwatt website	Website	Link
13	ENEREGATE webpage	IIECP website	Website	Link
14	GGGI Factsheet	GGGI website	Print materials	Link
15	ENEREGATE webpage	ENG website	Website	Link
16	ENEREGATE Press Release	NTUA website	Press release	Link
17	ENEREGATE project is featured in the Enlit projects directory	Enlit Website	Press release/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
18	ENEREGATE project is member of #SmartEnergyCluster	IIECP website	Press release	Link
19	ENEREGATE project is member of #SmartEnergyCluster	BD4NRG website	Press release/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
20	ENEREGATE project is member of #SmartEnergyCluster	MATRYCS website	Press release/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
21	ENEREGATE project is member of #SmartEnergyCluster	I-ENERGY website	Press release/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
22	Sustainable investments in the building sector: A critical review of financing tools and methods	9th International Symposium & 31st National Conference on Operational Research	Scientific Publication	Link
23	Investigating a Building Typology for Supporting Renovation Investments	9th International Symposium & 31st National Conference on Operational Research	Scientific Publication	Link
24	The #SmartEnergyCluster for a smart energy transition	V2MARKET newsletter	Newsletter	Link

#	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof
			Clustering activity: YES	
25	The #SmartEnergyCluster for a smart energy transition	SMartSPIN newsletter	Newsletter Clustering activity: YES	Link
26	Unlocking the Power of Collaboration: The #SmartEnergyCluster Driving the Smart Energy Transition	CINEA Website	Media article Clustering activity: YES	Link
27	ENERGATE 1 st Newsletter	ENERGATE website – newsletter page	Newsletter	Link
28	An Energy Efficiency Marketplace for Buildings: The ENERGATE System Architecture.	IISA 2023, Volos, Greece	Scientific Publication	Link
29	The LIFE projects come together in the Smart Energy Cluster to drive the smart energy transition.	Smartgridinfo	Press release	Link
30	Review on Financing Typologies of Building Renovation Projects	IEECP Website	Press release	Link
31	The #SmartEnergyCluster for a smart energy transition	EC Newsletter	Newsletter Clustering activity: YES	Link
32	The #SmartEnergyCluster for a smart energy transition	LIFE Programme Newsletter	Newsletter Clustering activity: YES	Link
33	ENERGATE Energy Efficiency Marketplace: the upcoming platform for investors and building managers	energypress.gr	Press release	Link
34	ENERGATE Press Release in GR	SCN Website	Press release	Link
35	MATRYCS H2020 and ENERGATE LIFE projects joining forces to incentivise energy efficiency in the building sector	MATRYCS website	Media article Clustering activity: YES	Link
36	Training workshop – September 28th, Madrid	IEECP Newsletter	Newsletter	Link
37	«Energy Efficiency Aggregation platform for Sustainable Investments – ENERGATE»	gargalianoionline.gr	Press release	Link
38	ENERGATE webpage	EnerSave Capital website	Website	Link
39	ENERGATE webpage	Riga Planning Region website	Website	Link

#	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof
40	Synergies	BD4NRG website	Media article Clustering activity: YES	Link
41	Synergies	MATRYCS website	Media article Clustering activity: YES	Link
42	ULI Spain and ENERATE Project Energy efficiency, from financing to implementation	ULI website	Media article Clustering activity: YES	Link
43	ENERATE 1 st ENERATE Regional Training Workshop in Madrid	NTUA website	Media article	Link
43	ENERATE Workshop Madrid	IEECP Newsletter	Newsletter	Link
45	ENERATE brochure	ENERATE website - communication materials	Print materials	Link
46	ENERATE poster	ENERATE website - communication materials	Print materials	Link
47	ENERATE Roll Up	ENERATE website - communication materials	Print materials	Link
48	ENERATE factsheet on Financing Typologies for Building Renovation	ENERATE website - communication materials	Print materials	Link
49	ENERATE infographic on Energy Efficiency Marketplace Use Cases	ENERATE website - communication materials	Print materials	Link
50	Update on ENERATE project topicalities	ENERATE	Media Article	Link
51	Global Green Growth Week 2023	ENERATE website	Press Release	Link
52	Energy efficiency investors and building managers to have a new go-to European marketplace	BIGG Newsletter	Newsletter/ Newsletter Clustering activity: YES	Link

#	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof
53	ENERGATE Project Expert Talk @ REHVA Supporters Committee	REHVA website	Press release	Link
54	ENERGATE's participation at REHVA's Brussel Summit	REHVA website	Press release	Link
55	Survey results (ENERGATE) – Financing energy efficiency in buildings: a survey to financiers, building owners, and implementors.	IEECP Newsletter	Newsletter	Link
56	#SmartEnergyCluster reference	Smart-Energy website	Media article/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
57	ENERGATE Regional Training Workshop in Madrid	NTUA website	Media article	Link
58	ENERGATE's Video on Financier	ENERGATE website and YouTube	Video	Link
59	ENERGATE's Video on Implementor	ENERGATE website and YouTube	Video	Link
60	ENERGATE's Video on Building Owner	ENERGATE website and YouTube	Video	Link
61	ENERGATE webpage	GREENESCO Website	Website	Link
62	ENERGATE Infographic on REHVA Brussels Summit Expert Talk	ENERGATE website	Print materials	Link
63	ENERGATE Expert Talk article published on REHVA Journal	ENERGATE website	Media article	Link
64	ENERGATE Newsletter, Issue December 2023	ENERGATE website	Newsletter	Link
65	A decision-making approach based on the TOPSIS method for supporting energy efficiency financing in buildings (submitted, to be published)	International Journal of Decision Support Systems, Decision Support Systems and Smart Technologies	Scientific Publication	Link
67	ENERGATE's Video on Public Bodies	ENERGATE website and YouTube	Video	Link
68	IEECP Newsletter	IEECP Newsletter	Newsletter	Link
69	ENERGATE CONSULTATION Survey	NTUA website	Media article	Link
70	ENERGATE Survey	SCN Website	Media Article	Link
71	ENERGATE Survey	SCN Newsletter	Newsletter	Link

#	Title	Venue/ Source	Type/Clustering Activity	Proof
72	ENERGATE & EN-TRACK Joint Webinar	ENERGATE Newsletter page	Press release	Link
73	Announcement for IISA 2024 - 4th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector	ENERGATE website	Press release	Link
74	4th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector	EUAGENDA website	Press release/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
75	EN-TRACK & ENERGATE projects' solutions for Enhanced Building Renovations	BuildUP website	Press release/ Article Clustering activity: YES	Link
76	ENERGATE Webpage	ENERBRAIN website	Website	Link
77	ENERGATE Webpage	GGGI website	Website	Link
78	4 th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector	CINEA website	Press release	Link
79	Article on REHVA website about webinar	REHVA website	Media article	Link
80	Promoting retrofitting projects in buildings: the designing steps of an online marketplace (Accepted)	EMCEI 2024, Marrakech, Morocco	Scientific Publication	Link
81	Utilising Decision – Making methods and online tools to accelerate sustainable renovation investments: Insights from a stakeholder engagement approach. (Accepted)	EURO 2024, Copenhagen, Denmark	Scientific Publication	Link
82	ENERGATEs' One Pager	ENERGATEs' website	Print materials	Link

Annex IX | Scientific publications

Table 9: ENERGate Scientific publications

Status	Publication
Published	Karakosta, C., Mylona, Z., Papathanasiou, J., & Psarras, J. (2023, May). Integrating Existing Knowledge to Accelerate Buildings Renovation Rates in Europe. In International Conference on Decision Support System Technology (pp. 124-136). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32534-2_10
	Kapsalis, P., Papapostolou, A., Touloumis, K., Andreoulaki, I., Mylona, Z., & Doukas, H. (2023, July). An Energy Efficiency Marketplace for Buildings: The ENERGate System Architecture. In 2023 14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/IISA59645.2023.10345882.
Presented in Conference – Proceedings to be published	Andreoulaki, I., Papapostolou, A., Karakosta, C., Mexis, F. D., Psarras, J. (2023, June). Sustainable Investments in the Building Sector: A Critical Review of Financing Tools and Methods. In 2023 9th International Symposium & 31st National Conference on Operational Research Book of Abstracts HELORS 2023
	Papapostolou, A., Andreoulaki, I., Touloumis, K., Kapsalis, P., Psarras, J. (2023, June). Investigating a Building Typology for Supporting Renovation Investments. In 2023 9th International Symposium & 31st National Conference on Operational Research Book of Abstracts HELORS 2023
Accepted to be presented in Conference	Papapostolou, A., Andreoulaki, I., Kotrogiannis, V., Psarras J. (2024, June – July). Utilising Decision-Making methods and online tools to accelerate sustainable renovation investments: Insights from a stakeholder engagement approach. In 2024 33rd EURO Conference EURO 2024
	Andreoulaki, I., Papapostolou, A., Kotrogiannis, V., Marinakis, V. (2024, May). Promoting retrofitting projects in buildings: the designing steps of an online marketplace. In 2024 6 th Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration (EMCEI) EMCEI - Euro-Mediterranean Conference for Environmental Integration
Submitted	Andreoulaki, I., Papapostolou, A., Karakosta, C., Marinakis, V. A decision-making approach based on the TOPSIS method for supporting energy efficiency financing in buildings. submitted (December, 2024) to the Special Issue on: "Decision Support Systems and Smart Technologies" organised by International Journal of Decision Support Systems International Journal of Decision Support Systems
Invited papers – to be submitted	Extension of the paper: Kapsalis, P., Papapostolou, A., Touloumis, K., Andreoulaki, I., Mylona, Z., & Doukas, H. (2023, July). An Energy Efficiency

	<p>Marketplace for Buildings: The ENERGATE System Architecture. In 2023 14th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA) (pp. 1-6). IEEE. doi: 10.1109/IISA59645.2023.10345882.</p> <p>has been invited and will be submitted to the Special Issue on Computing, Engineering and Multidisciplinary Sciences organised by Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal (ASTESJ)</p> <p>Special Issue on Computing, Engineering and Multidisciplinary Sciences - Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal</p>
	<p>ENERGATE will contribute a conference paper to the following:</p> <p>2024 15th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems & Applications (IISA). 4th International Workshop on Data Analytics in the Energy Sector</p> <p>4th International Workshop on Big Data Analytics in the Energy IISA 2024</p>

OUR TEAM

Project Coordinator

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